

EMPOWERING RURAL PEOPLE FOR EXCELLENCE THROUGH EDUCATION

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Abstract

The concept of learning system is required to be changed keeping in mind the fast changing scenario of education; it should be user friendly and excellence based. People become empower by very wide range of areas. This is true that in future those people will be winning who have some different ability, wide knowledge of the subject field and deep particularity. To think around this problem the researcher has decided to work on empowering rural people for excellence through education. By this new era people will learn easily, more deeply and with more interest according to their condition, requirement and convenience.

Main objective of this study is empowering rural people for excellence through ICT education using their local need & environment.

The experiment has been done on tribal Valsad district. People of four villages were considered as the population. The technique of sampling called “purposive sampling” was applied for the experiment. The knowledge about the use of ICT in their field & daily work were provided through Guidance, demonstration and experiments during 5 weeks daily 2 hours.

By administering practical observation and use of applications- ICT in their field & daily work, the data collection was completed. The analysis was carried out with the help of simple statistics.

Researcher will humbly efforts on that direction that the people will work with interest & speed so the quality & comfort ability increases and due to these the ability of people will become stronger.

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KEYWORDS : Empower, Excellence, ICT, Technology

INTRODUCTION

The concept of learning system is required to be changed keeping in mind the fast changing scenario of education, it should be user friendly and excellence based. People become empower by very wide range of areas. This is true that in future those people will be winning who have some different ability, wide knowledge of the subject field and deep particularity. To think around this problem the researcher has decided to work on empowering rural people for excellence through education. By this new era people will learn easily, more deeply and with more interest according to their condition, requirement and convenience. Many of the Indian villagers were poor in utilizing information technologies for communication and information needs. To make information technology and electronic communication network is more accessible to rural population to collect and disseminate information

beyond national boundaries; more emphasis should be given in the development of information technologies, especially in the remote rural areas.

There were thirty three districts in Gujarat state of India, in which one of the tribal districts is Valsad. In which Kaparadataluka of valsad district is remote and very backward till today. It is difficult to have a road in many villages. The geographical situation of this area is surprising. This area is full of mountains and hills. Though the maximum rain of Gujarat falls in this area, there is a shortage of water. The streets clustered in 4-5 houses and the streets were far from one another. The streets were situated at the slope of the mountains. So, Investigator has decided to study empowering these people for excellence through education of ICT.

In this study researcher has been planned to select those rural people who studied below 12th standard and working as a farmer with age group 30 to 50 years. Empowering them “use of mobile applications” is selected as medium. According to their local environment and needs, recharging of mobile & dish TV, pay the bills, money transfer using SBI Buddy, online bank account operating and email/ online application, net surfing for their requirements were included in module. The main aim of this study is to give speed and comfortability to the tribal people.

OBJECTIVE

1. To empower the poor tribal people by education of ICT

LIMITATIONS

1. Present study is carried out on four villages of tribal Kaparadataluka.
2. Age group of 30 to 50 years farmers were included.

MATHODOLOGY

(1) POPULATION AND SAMPLE

There were six taluka tribal Valsad district, in which one of the most tribal taluka is Kaparada. There were 294 villages in the Kaparadataluka. The technique of sampling called “purposive sampling” was applied for the experiment. Population contains that age group 30 to 50 year’s rural people who studied below 12th standard and working as a farmer. Sample contains 76 people from four villages Chandvengan, Mandva, Kastuniya and Takuniya.

(2) RESEARCH TOOLS (Medium)

- (1) Mobile applications like SBI Buddy and Google chrome.

(3) PROCEDURE

First meeting was introduction and producing the trust in respondents. During the five weeks researcher had humbly tried to familiar respondents with the mobile applications and their easy use. Experiment contains Recharge mobile & Dish TV, money transfer, pay electricity bill with the help of SBI buddy. Use of Debit card will help in online purchase of seeds, fertilizers and pesticides from JillaSahakariMandal. See News in local language, songs and bhajajns using mobile. The present study is the review of experimental research work done by Navsarjan Foundation. The experiment was continued alternately for 5 weeks for daily 2 hours.

(4) DATA COLLECTION AND ANALYSIS

Data collection was conducted by continuous observation to respondent about using of ICT in their routine life. The analysis was carried out with the help of simple statistics tools.

(5) INTERPRETATION AND FINDINGS

The Sample distribution details have been given in the following tables.

No	App	Area	Respondent Village wise								Total	
			Chandvengan		Mandva		Kastuniya		Takuniya			
			M	F	M	F	M	F	M	F	M	F
1	SBI buddy	Recharge mobile	12	07	14	11	08	06	11	07	45	31
		Dish TV	12	03	12	04	08	02	11	03	43	12
		money transfer	03	01	04	00	03	03	06	03	16	07
		pay electricity bill	12	06	14	10	08	06	11	07	45	29
2	Debit Card	Online purchase	08	01	07	02	04	01	05	01	24	05
3	Email		12	07	14	11	08	06	11	07	45	31
4	YouTube		12	07	14	11	08	06	11	07	45	31

Table shows that most of the respondents were successfully using SBI buddy for recharge the mobile. They respond that it is very easy and time saving. Also they save money because local retailer who charged them extra for service. In this factor 100% male and female had positive response.

The respondents were successfully using SBI buddy for recharge the Dish TV. Although they responded that it was very easy and time saving, female were not interested because they thought that it was the responsibility of male.

Very few using money transfer by SBI buddy because their ward were using debit/credit card. The respondents were successfully using SBI buddy to pay electricity bill. They responded that it was very easy and time saving. They felt that now they were free from tired job for waiting in a line. In this factor male and female have positive response.

Average respondents liked to use Debit card for online purchase of seeds, fertilizers and pesticides from JillaSahakariMandal. One reason is that they were afraid from their experiences from Mandal. They also afraid from online fraud incidences in society.

The respondents were successfully using E-mail and YouTube. They responded that it was very easy and rapid. In this factor 100% male and female have positive response. They promised that now they will use e-mail for communication with their ward and relatives and also use YouTube.

They live in society which is located in surrounding of 30 k.m. radius. Many of them had never traveled by train. So, there is no need of online train ticket reservation.

(6) CONCLUSIONS

The main objective of this study is to empower rural people (Studied up to 12thstd) for excellence through ICT education using their local need & environment. Researcher would humbly effort on that direction of tribal people would work with their interest so the quality & comfortability increases and due to this the ability of people will become stronger. Researcher had found that the farmers were empowered by themselves for excellence and through ICT education using their local need & environment.

(7) ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

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